

Preparation and characterization of new hybrid organic-inorganic nanoporous silica for removal of Cu^{II}, Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} from aqueous media

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Abstract : Amino functional nanoporous silica MCM-48 materials have been synthesized to develop efficient adsorbents of heavy metals in wastewater. Functionalization with amino groups such as 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl amine (TMSPA) and tetraethylenpentamine (TEPA) has been carried out by using the grafting method. Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), nitrogen adsorption-desorption and Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy methods were performed to gain an understanding of the structure and surface properties of the nanoporous silica materials. Metal removal from aqueous solution has been examined for Cu^{II}, Pb^{II} and Cd^{II}. It was found that amino-modified ordered nanoporous silica materials show significant adsorption for heavy metals. The effect of various parameters was conducted to study the adsorption of heavy metal ions onto MCM-48 modified with amine group from an aqueous solution for the effect of pH and contact time in batch systems. The kinetic analysis indicated that the adsorption process was successfully fitted with the pseudo-first order kinetic model. Langmuir and Freundlich models were used for a mathematical description of the adsorption isotherm. The equilibrium process was explained well by the Freundlich isotherm.

Keywords : Nanoporous silica adsorbent, tetraethylenpentamine, 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl amine, heavy metals, adsorption isotherm.

Introduction

Pollution of aqueous systems by heavy metal ions is considered a major environmental problem that requires immediate solution. Heavy metal ions such as lead and cadmium are extremely harmful to living cells. Hazards of these environmental pollutants are known and well documented¹. Conventional methods for the removal of heavy metal ions in aqueous solutions include electrochemical treatment, ion exchange, reverse osmosis, chemical precipitation and adsorption. Particularly, adsorption is known as one of the best methods for the removal of low concentrations of heavy metals². Although the activated carbon material is used as a general adsorbent for organic and inorganic structures, research and development of new adsorbents are needed to improve the effectiveness of adsorption at very low pollutant concentrations. For this objective, new hybrid organic-inorganic mesoporous ordered structures have recently been sug-

gested as substitute adsorbents for the removal of heavy metal ions. Mesoporous materials are a subset of nanoporous materials that were examined by the Mobil oil researchers in 1992^{3,4} and from that time, mesoporous silica materials have been used for many applications. Mesoporous silica materials, such as SBA-15, MCM-41 and MCM-48, have homogeneous pore sizes and large surface areas⁵⁻⁸. Furthermore, the surface of mesoporous silica materials can be easily modified with organic groups to achieve specific purposes and change their characteristics⁹⁻¹². These materials have been developed and successfully used in the removal of heavy metal ions, such as lead from aqueous media¹³⁻¹⁶. Most of the reported researches about this matter have been concerned to the modification with propylthiol and other thio-groups in order to remove heavy metal ions such as mercury from water¹⁷⁻²¹. However, other heavy metals are more efficiently adsorbed into various families of mesoporous or-

dered silicas modified with organic chains containing one or more amino groups^{22–25}. Within this group of mesoporous silica, MCM-48 is typical, with its large surface area (700–1200 m² g⁻¹) and large pore volume, with a regular cubic structure and uniform and tunable pore size (2–50 nm), which can be a reliable support for designing adsorbents^{26,27}.

In this study, a new nanoporous material MCM-48 modified with amine groups, such as 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl amine (TMSPA) and tetraethylenpentamine (TEPA) was synthesized and its adsorption behavior for heavy metal ions Cu^{II}, Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} was investigated. It was found that these adsorbent show good adsorption for heavy metal ions. The textural properties and structural order of the nanoporous materials were studied by nitrogen adsorption and XRD. The presence of amino functional groups on the surface of nanoporous silica was confirmed by means of FTIR analysis. The influence of several operating parameters for adsorption of heavy metal ions, such as chemical modification, pH, contact time and initial concentration were investigated in batch mode. The equilibrium data are fitted into Freundlich and Langmuir equations in order to specify the correlation between the experimental data and isotherm models. The experimental data was also examined using first and second order kinetic models and the kinetic constants were calculated.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

The reactants used in this study were tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) as a silica source, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) as a surfactant, sodium hydroxide (NaOH), sodium fluoride (NaF) for synthesis of nanoporous silica (MCM-48), tetraethylenpentamine and ethanol for functionalization of nanoporous silica (MCM-48/TEPA), 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl amine and dry toluene were used to prepare modified nanoporous silica (MCM-48/TMSPA). Sources of metals for sorption experiments were lead nitrate, copper nitrate and cadmium nitrate of synthesis grade. All chemicals were of analytical grade obtained from Merck (Germany).

Synthesis of nanoporous silica (MCM-48) :

MCM-48 was prepared according to the procedure

described by Ref. 28. In a representative synthesis, the MCM-48 was prepared as follows : 10 ml of tetraethyl orthosilicate was mixed with 50 ml of deionized water and the mixture was stirred for 45 min at 308 K, then 0.9 g of sodium hydroxide and 0.19 g sodium fluoride were added into the mixture. After another 60 min, 10.61 g of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide was added to the mixture, and further stirring continued for another 60 min. The mixture was heated for 24 h at 393 K in an autoclave under static conditions, and the final product was filtered, washed with deionized water and dried at 373 K. The samples were then calcined in air for 4 h with increasing the temperature to 823 K at 1 °C/min of the heating rate.

Synthesis of MCM-48 functionalized with 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl amine :

The grafting modification method was employed in this study. In 70 mL of dry toluene, 0.1 g of MCM-48 was suspended and 2 mL of 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl amine was added under a dry nitrogen atmosphere. The mixture was then refluxed for 12 h. The solid product was filtered, washed with dichloromethane and ethanol, and was dried. It was then soxhlet extracted with mixture of ethanol and dichloromethane (1 : 1), in order to remove the silylating reagent residue, and dried overnight at 70 °C under a vacuum and denoted as MCM-48/TMSPA.

Synthesis of MCM-48 functionalized with tetraethylenpentamine :

In 50 g ethanol, 1 g of tetraethylenpentamine (TEPA) was dissolved under stirring for 40 min at room temperature and then 2 g mesoporous silica was added. After refluxing for 4 h, the resulting mixture was evaporated at 80 °C. Finally, the products were dried in air for 1 h at 100 °C and denoted as MCM-48/TEPA.

Characterization of synthesized amine-functionalized silica MCM-48 :

Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K were measured by using a Micromeritics model ASAP 2010 sorptometer to characterize textural properties. The pore size distribution was obtained from the adsorption branch by means of the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (B.J.H.) model

with cylindrical geometry of the pores and surface area was calculated by using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (B.E.T.) equation. Mesoscopic order was investigated by low-angle X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). The patterns of the samples were obtained on Philips 1830 diffractometer using the Cu-K α line. The diffractograms were recorded in the 2 θ range of 1–10 with a 2 θ step size of 0.01°. The Fourier transform infrared spectra (FT-IR) for the synthesis materials were measured under attenuated total reflection mode on a DIGILAB FTS 7000 instrument.

Heavy metal adsorption experiments :

Adsorption behavior was examined by a batch method, which permits appropriate assessment of parameters that influence the adsorption process such as contact time, chemical modification, initial concentration and solution pH. A series of aqueous solutions of heavy metal with the same pH and their concentration ranging from 10 to 100 mg L⁻¹ were prepared by dissolving pure analytes in double distilled water. In order to examine the heavy metal removal ability of the modified nanoporous materials a set of adsorption experiments was done by stirring 0.01 g of functionalized nanoporous MCM-48 in 25 mL of a single metal solution. Adsorbent-solution mixtures were stirred for 2 h and then filtered. The aqueous systems selected were Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pb^{II}. The metal salts used were nitrates in all cases. Metal concentration, both in the final and initial solutions, was determined by atomic adsorption spectroscopy (AAS). The amount of heavy metals adsorbed per unit mass of the q_e (mg g⁻¹) was calculated by the following equation :

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)V}{W} \quad (1)$$

where q_e is the adsorption capacity (mg g⁻¹) of the adsorbent at equilibrium; C_e and C_0 are the equilibrium and the initial concentrations of solute (mg L⁻¹), respectively; V is the volume of the solution (L) and W is the mass (g) of adsorbent used in the experiments.

Adsorption kinetics of heavy metals :

For the adsorption kinetics measurement of heavy metals onto adsorbent, 25 ml of the heavy metals solution with an initial concentration of 10 mg L⁻¹ was trans-

ferred into a flask and mixed with 0.01 g of amino-modified ordered nanoporous silica materials. Samples were taken from the solution by filtration at different time intervals. The concentration of heavy metals in the residual solution was determined and the amount of adsorption (q_t) was calculated according to eq. (2).

$$q_t = \frac{(C_0 - C_t)V}{W} \quad (2)$$

where q_t is the amount of adsorption at time t , C_0 is the initial concentration of heavy metal in the solution, C_t is the concentration of heavy metal in the solution at time t , V is the volume of the solution, and m is the mass of amino-modified ordered nanoporous silica materials (MCM-48/TMSPA or MCM-48/TEPA).

Results and discussion

Physical and chemical properties of the adsorbents :

N₂ adsorption/desorption was conducted to observe the effect of the functionalization with various amine groups on the specific surface area and size of pores. Fig. 1 shows the adsorption-desorption isotherms of MCM-48 and hybrid organic-inorganic nanoporous silica MCM-48.

All synthesis materials matched the type IV hysteresis loop of the IUPAC classification. The shape of the hysteresis loop was maintained, although the amount of nitrogen adsorbed decreased, this means that the pore shape had not been changed during the modification. The pore sizes and the specific surface areas of the adsorbents, both without and with modification with amine groups, are presented in Table 1. The specific surface area and pore size of the non-functionalized MCM-48 were 1312 m² g⁻¹ and 3.1 nm, respectively. Accordingly the pore size and the surface area were decreased after adding the functional amine groups and with increasing length of the formed amine chain.

In order to check the structural degradation, XRD data of MCM-48 and amino-functionalized nanoporous silica materials were obtained on Philips 1830 diffractometer using Cu-K α radiation of wavelength 0.154 nm. Fig. 2 shows the XRD peaks of the samples. The

Fig. 1. Adsorption-desorption isotherms of nitrogen at 77 K over MCM-48, MCM-48/TMSPA and MCM-48/TEPA.

Table 1. Textural properties determined from nitrogen adsorption-desorption experiments at 77 K

Adsorbent	<i>d</i> spacing (nm)	<i>A</i> _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	<i>V</i> _p (cm ³ g ⁻¹)
MCM-48	3.1	1312.6	1.22
MCM-48/TMSPA	2.6	574.8	0.65
MCM-48/TEPA	2.4	528.3	0.53

XRD patterns of MCM-48 exhibit two peaks at 2θ smaller than 3° and a series of weak peaks in the range $3.5\text{--}5.5^\circ$ as expected for MCM-48 phase. They are assigned to the (2 1 1), (2 2 0), (4 2 0), (3 3 2) and (4 2 2) reflections on

the Ia_3d space group. The peaks obtained in this study for MCM-48/TMSPA and MCM-48/TEPA highly matches with the similar peaks reported in Refs. 29, 30.

Qualitative identification of functional groups was accomplished by FT-IR spectroscopy. Fig. 3 shows the FT-IR spectrum of unfunctionalized and amino-functionalized MCM-48 materials over the range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A broad band in the range of $3700\text{--}3037\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is seen which can be attributed to the framework of Si-OH group interaction with the defect sites and adsorbed water molecules.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of MCM-48 (a), MCM-48/TEPA (b) and MCM-48/TMSPA (c).

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of MCM-48/TEPA (a), MCM-48 (b) and MCM-48/TMSPA (c).

The Si-OH peak appears at about 3409 cm^{-1} , while peaks for the weak single Si-OH groups derived from the germinal Si-OH groups were observed at 3708 cm^{-1} . The asymmetric stretching vibrations of Si-O-Si and Si-OH are observed by the absorption bands at $900\text{--}1529\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the band at 790.68 cm^{-1} is assigned to free silica. In general, the functionalized silica with amino groups show a broad NH_2 symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations at $3050\text{--}3650\text{ cm}^{-1}$, an N-H deformation peak at $1625\text{--}1434\text{ cm}^{-1}$, C-H stretches of methyl groups at $3000\text{--}2850$ and 1467 cm^{-1} . In addition, in comparison with the MCM-48/TEPA, the amino bands are weaker for MCM-48/TMSPA.

Metal ion adsorption studies :

Effect of chemical modification and the initial metal concentration :

An adsorption experiment was done to examine the effects of the amine groups, introduced to the nanoporous silica materials. Comparative experiments were performed using the same method for the nanoporous silica materials without functionalization. As shown in Fig. 4, the capacities for Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} -ion adsorption by the nonfunctionalized adsorbents were relatively low. When

all the nanoporous silica materials were functionalized with APTES or TEPA, the amounts of metal ion adsorbed were greatly increased.

The initial analyte concentration provides a significant driving force to overcome mass transfer resistance of analyte between the solid and aqueous phases.

Fig. 5 shows the percentage of heavy metal ion removal for a range of Cd, Pb and Cu ion concentrations. Metal ion removal percentage increases when the initial ion concentration decreases. At low metal ion concentrations the ratio of surface active site to the total metal ions in the solution is high and therefore metal ions may interact with the adsorbent and be removed from the solution. At higher initial metal ion concentration ($>100\text{ ppm}$), more metal ion was left in solution due to the saturation of the binding site.

This result indicates that in the modified MCM-48, -NH_2 groups were readily available and easily accessible probably because the nanoporous surfaces of MCM-48- NH_2 facilitated the metal ion transportation in the adsorption process. On the other hand, Fig. 5 also indicate that the effective sorbent for the removal of cadmium and lead is mesoporous MCM-48 modified with TEPA with an affinity equal to 90% for 10 ppm and the effective

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. Effect of chemical modification on adsorption of (a) Cu, (b) Cd and (c) Pb onto different mesoporous silicates (adsorbent dosage = 0.4 g L⁻¹, contact time = 2 h).

sorbent for the removal of copper is mesoporous MCM-48 modified with TMSPA with an affinity equal to 99% for 10 ppm.

Effect of the pH :

Effect of pH on the removal of heavy metals on MCM-

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5. Effect of initial solution concentration on adsorption of (a) Cu, (b) Cd and (c) Pb onto different mesoporous silicates (adsorbent dosage = 0.4 g L⁻¹, contact time = 2 h).

48/TMSPA and MCM-48/TEPA was investigated in the pH ranges of 2–7 (initial concentration = 10 mg L⁻¹, adsorbent dose 0.4 g L⁻¹, contact time = 2 h). The aqueous solution pH is an effective parameter in the adsorption process because of its effect on, the concentration of

the counter metal ions on the functional groups of the adsorbent, the solubility of the heavy metal ions and the degree of ionization of the adsorbent during the reaction³¹. It can be observed that the highest adsorption of heavy metals with functionalized MCM-48 was obtained at final pH > 3. With the pH increased from 3.0 to 5.0, the heavy metals adsorbed increased. The variations in the amount of heavy metals adsorbed with pH could be explained on the basis of competition between the heavy metal and H₃O⁺ ions for adsorption sites on amino-modified ordered nanoporous silica. At low pH, the number of H₃O⁺ exceeds that of the metal ions several times and the surface is most likely covered with H₃O⁺ ions, which account for less metal ions adsorption. When pH increases, more and more H₃O⁺ ions leave the adsorbent surface making the sites available to the metal ions adsorption. The optimum pH value for the removal of metal ions from aqueous solution ranged from 5 to 6.

The effect of contact time on the adsorption procedure :

In this study effect of contact time on removal of heavy metal on MCM-48/TEPA and MCM-48/TMSPA (adsorbent dosage = 0.4 g L⁻¹) was investigated as an important influence on the adsorption of analytes. Optimum contact time for adsorbents was obtained at 120 min.

It is obvious that during the initial stage in the process, a greater number of adsorption sites were available to the metal ions, enabling them to interact readily with the adsorbent and hence leading to a high adsorption rate. The slow adsorption rate observed during the latter stages of the process may be attributed to the slower rate of diffusion of the solute into the interior of the adsorbent particles. In fact, the adsorption rate was dependent on the rate of the metal ions were transported from the bulk liquid phase to the present adsorption sites. This effect is important, as equilibrium time is one of the significant parameters for an economical wastewater treatment system.

Adsorption isotherm :

The equilibrium adsorption isotherms are one of the essential data to understand the mechanism of the adsorption systems. Freundlich and Langmuir models are the most often used for describing sorption isotherms. The Langmuir isotherm model is based on assumptions of adsorption homogeneity such as monolayer surface cov-

erage, no interaction between adsorbed species and equally available adsorption sites. The Langmuir equation can be described by the linearized eq. (3)³².

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{q_m b} + \frac{1}{q_m} C_e \quad (3)$$

where q_e is the amount of solute sorbed per unit weight of sorbent (mg g⁻¹), C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg L⁻¹), q_m is the Langmuir constant, which represents the saturated monolayer sorption capacity (mg g⁻¹), b (L mg⁻¹) is a constant related to the energy of adsorption.

The Freundlich isotherm model can be used to nonideal sorption on heterogeneous surfaces as well as multilayer sorption³³. The empirical Freundlich equation can also be transformed into linearized eq. (4).

$$\ln q_e = \ln K_F + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \ln C_e \quad (4)$$

where q_e is the amount of solute sorbed per unit weight of sorbent (mg g⁻¹), K_F is the Freundlich constant related to the adsorption capacity, n is relevant to the adsorption intensity, and C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg L⁻¹).

The linearized form of Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherms obtained were presented in Figs. 6 and 7 respectively and the adsorption constants considered from the isotherms with the correlation coefficients (R^2) were given in Table 2.

It can be seen that Freundlich isotherm fits the data better than Langmuir isotherm. The MCM-48/TMSPA and MCM-48/TEPA adsorbents used in this study had a relatively large adsorption capacity. Ultimately, we can conclude that modified MCM-48 materials are effective to remove heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions.

Adsorption kinetics :

Adsorption rate has been examined by using two common semi-empirical kinetic models which are based on adsorption equilibrium capacity : the pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order equations, proposed by Lagergren and Ho and McKay respectively^{34,35}.

Pseudo-first order equation relates the adsorption rate to the heavy metal ion adsorbed amount at time t as :

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (5)$$

where q_e and q_t are amounts of metal ion adsorbed (mg

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

(c)

(c)

Fig. 6. Langmuir isotherm for adsorption of (a) Cd^{II}, (b) Pb^{II} and (c) Cu^{II} on MCM-48/TEPA and MCM-48/TMSPA adsorbent.

g^{-1}) at equilibrium and time t (min), respectively, and k_1 is the rate constant of pseudo-first order adsorption (min^{-1}).

The k_1 values and q_e were calculated from the slope and intercept from the plots of $\log (q_e - q_t)$ versus t for different adsorbent. These values and the correlation coefficient are given in Table 3. Also, the calculated q_e

Fig. 7. Freundlich isotherm for adsorption of (a) Cd^{II}, (b) Pb^{II} and (c) Cu^{II} on MCM-48/TEPA and MCM-48/TMSPA adsorbent.

values agree with the experimental data ($q_{e,\text{exp}}$). This indicates that the adsorption perfectly complies with the

Table 2. Langmuir and Freundlich constants for adsorption heavy metal ions by MCM-48/TEPA and MCM-48/TMSPA adsorbents

Adsorbate	Adsorbent	Langmuir constants			Freundlich constants		
		q_m (mg g ⁻¹)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	R^2	K_F (mg g ⁻¹)	n (L mg ⁻¹)	R^2
Cd ^{II}	MCM-48/TMSPA	147.05	0.033	0.9896	7.533	1.55	0.9962
	MCM-48/TEPA	204.08	0.063	0.9657	17.23	1.66	0.9972
Cu ^{II}	MCM-48/TMSPA	86.20	0.620	0.9983	39.57	5.053	0.9935
	MCM-48/TEPA	70.42	0.03	0.9807	17.489	4.28	0.9927
Pb ^{II}	MCM-48/TMSPA	111.11	0.038	0.9928	6.5528	1.579	0.994
	MCM-48/TEPA	129.87	0.153	0.9938	20.92	1.96	0.9903

Table 3. Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order constants for the removal heavy metals by MCM-48/TEPA and MCM-48/TMSPA adsorbents

Adsorbate	Adsorbent (50 ppm)	Cd ^{II}		Pb ^{II}		Cu ^{II}	
		MCM-48/ TMSPA	MCM-48/ TEPA	MCM-48/ TMSPA	MCM-48/ TEPA	MCM-48/ TMSPA	MCM-48/ TEPA
Pseudo-first order constants	$q_{e,cal}$ (mg g ⁻¹)	66.207	88.16	54	93.15	81.06	42.275
	k_1 (g (mg min) ⁻¹)	0.0091	0.0089	0.0099	0.0091	0.0104	0.0106
	R^2	0.9927	0.9915	0.9903	0.9904	0.9922	0.9949
Pseudo-second order constants	$q_{e,cal}$ (mg g ⁻¹)	250	175.43	196.078	243.09	232.55	222.22
	k_2 (g (mg min) ⁻¹)	6.38×10^{-6}	2.57×10^{-5}	1.011×10^{-5}	1.155×10^{-5}	1.021×10^{-5}	4.029×10^{-6}
	R^2	0.7972	0.8436	0.8449	0.8702	0.8939	0.7196
	$q_{e,exp}$ (mg g ⁻¹)	61.6	87.5	55.4	90.62	76	37.5

pseudo-first order reaction.

The pseudo-second order kinetic model is as following :

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \left(\frac{1}{q_e} \right) t \quad (6)$$

where k_2 is the rate constant of pseudo-second order adsorption (g (mg min)⁻¹).

The q_e and k_2 values were calculated from the slope and intercept from a plot of (t/q_t) versus t for the pseudo-second order model given in eq. (6), respectively. The $q_{e,exp}$ values do not agree with calculated ones, obtained from the plots. It is obvious from Table 3 that pseudo-first order model is not suitable to explain the kinetic profile of the adsorption of metal ions onto modified nanoporous silica because of the apparent lack of linear behavior.

Table 3 shows that the correlation coefficients of first order kinetics model are greater than second order kinetics.

Conclusion

In this study, novel nanoporous silica materials with amine group named as MCM-48/TEPA and MCM-48/TMSPA was successfully prepared for effective removal of Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Cu²⁺ from aqueous solution. Influence of parameters such as solution pH, contact time and initial concentration (10–100 mg L⁻¹) on adsorption capacity has been investigated and optimized. The sorption equilibrium was reached within 120 min. The structural order and textural properties of the synthesized material was studied by XRD, FT-IR and nitrogen adsorption-desorption analysis. Furthermore, isotherms and kinetics of adsorption of Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Cu²⁺ on modified nanoporous silica were investigated and the results re-

vealed that the adsorption process followed a pseudo-first order rate equation and better fitted Freundlich adsorption.

The hybrid material MCM-48/TEPA showed higher adsorption selectivity for Pb^{2+} and Cd^{2+} compared to other metal ions with an affinity equal to 90% for 10 ppm and the hybrid material MCM-48/TMSPA showed higher adsorption selectivity for Cu^{2+} with an affinity equal to 99% for 10 ppm. The high density of the organic groups grafted on the MCM-48 surface resulted in remarkable adsorption capacities for heavy metal ions. Therefore, the modified nanoporous materials are considered a potential adsorbent for the removal of heavy metal ions from wastewater.

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